

Rethinking the mobile edge for vehicular services

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ABSTRACT

The growing connected car market requires mobile network operators (MNOs) to rethink their network architecture to deliver ultra-reliable low-latency communications. In response, Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) has emerged as a solution, enabling the deployment of computing resources at the network edge. For MNOs to tap into the potential benefits of MEC, they need to transform their networks accordingly. Consequently, the primary objective of this study is to design a realistic MEC architecture and corresponding optimal *deployment* strategy – deciding on the *placement* and *configuration* of computing resources – as opposed to prior studies focusing on MEC run-time management and orchestration (e.g., service placement, computation offloading, and user allocation). To cater to the heterogeneous demands of vehicular services, we propose a multi-tier MEC architecture aligned with 5G and Beyond-5G radio access network deployments. Therefore, we frame MEC deployment as an optimization problem within this architecture, assuming 3 MEC tiers. Our data-driven evaluation, grounded in realistic assumptions about network architecture, usage, latency, and cost models, relies on datasets from a major MNO in the UK. We show the benefits of adopting a 3-tier MEC architecture over single-tier (centralized or distributed) architectures for heterogeneous vehicular services, in terms of deployment cost, energy consumption, and robustness.

1. Introduction

The last decade of innovation and standardization in 5G have brought advancements to every aspect of cellular systems. However, like any emerging technology, the pace of real-world deployments does not instantly match the pace of innovation [1,2]. For Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), the high costs associated with deploying, configuring, and operating 5G network and cloud-edge computing components without a clear business strategy for innovative use cases, remain a major hurdle towards realizing the 5G vision.

Among the services enabled by 5G and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks, connected cars (hereafter *cars*) and Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) services – such as assisted and remote driving – are among the most promising use cases. Cars are increasingly using mobile networks, and their market is one of the highest-growth Internet of Things (IoT) areas, with Ericsson predicting 500 million connected cars by 2025 [3–6]. This growing and valuable market has triggered close inter-working between telco and automotive industry sectors, reflected in the creation of joint fora, e.g., the Automobile Edge Computing Consortium (AECC), initially formed by Toyota, Intel, and Ericsson, and the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA), with 116 members dedicated to the design of systems that satisfy the demands of connected car services.

As also stated by the 5GAA [3], the success of C-V2X services is contingent on Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and MEC [7]. MEC is a promising solution to provide low-latency and efficient data processing capabilities, as required by the majority of C-V2X services, by re-purposing the existing infrastructure at the network edge to host computing resources, ultimately complementing the cloud computing approach. To successfully execute this 5G vision, MNOs must thus undertake a network transformation and capitalize on the potential advantages provided by MEC, while concurrently reducing both the cost and energy footprint of their network.

Within the above context, MNOs encounter two primary challenges: formulating a strategy for the initial MEC deployment and for managing such MEC at runtime. Solutions for MEC runtime management and orchestration often assume a pre-deployed MEC and have been extensively analyzed (e.g., [8–12] for resource/user allocation, [13–15] for service placement/migration, and [16–19] for computation offloading). MEC deployment differs from these solutions due to its one-time nature, with minimal changes expected thereafter. At the same time, it is critical for MNOs as the performance of run-time management and orchestration depend heavily on MEC deployment.

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Fig. 1. Example of a 3-tier MEC deployment. MEC instances closer to base stations exhibit lower latency (lighter colors). However, they are costly and offer fewer resources and connections to the base stations. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

In this paper, our goal is to provide a realistic MEC deployment strategy in 5G/B5G systems, in terms of MEC *placement* and *configuration*, from the point of view of MNOs supporting C-V2X services. These services are indeed among the most challenging use cases (in terms of latency and reliability) that MNOs are expected to support in their MEC-integrated networks, as also highlighted by the ongoing discussions across telco, automotive, and standardization communities [3,20,21], mentioned above and further detailed in Section 4.3. First, in order to cater to the heterogeneous demands of C-V2X services [5], we design a 3-tier MEC architecture, depicted on a high level in Fig. 1, and address its realistic alignment onto 5G/B5G Radio Access Network (RAN) architectures (i.e., NG-RAN [22]). We then determine an optimal MEC deployment strategy, where we place and configure the MEC servers among three tiers, considering that higher tiers – being more distant to users – offer more computing resources with lower cost, at the expense of higher latency. We thus formulate MEC deployment as an optimization problem to minimize deployment and energy costs while satisfying C-V2X service demands. Unlike the prior work on MEC deployment that minimizes only latency instead of cost [23–25], or overlooked service heterogeneity [26–28] and/or the NG-RAN architecture [29–31], our work is the first to demonstrate how to optimally select MEC server locations onto a realistic network architecture and how to configure such servers towards building an effective MEC platform for heterogeneous C-V2X services. Moreover, thanks to our data-driven approach, we embed in our analysis realistic assumptions and models on different aspects of MEC deployment for C-V2X services, thus significantly enhancing previous work that considered abstract assumptions such as using the same latency budget for all services [32–34].

The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- We design a realistic data-driven multi-tier MEC architecture and the corresponding optimal deployment strategy to cater to the heterogeneous demands of vehicular services (Section 5.1). We consider three C-V2X service models [35] already reflected in real-world traffic patterns (Section 4), and an underlying network infrastructure that maps onto standardized 5G/B5G NG-RAN architectures [22].
- To reflect the reality of running a production mobile network, we formulate the multi-tier MEC deployment as an optimization problem that considers both service requirements and costs (Section 6.2). To do so, we build realistic latency and cost models based on both our collected dataset and extensive reviews of relevant, measurement-based analyses, aiming to contrast and propose: (i) a comprehensive latency model (Section 5.2); (ii) current-market values for MEC-hosting servers; and (iii) real-world average energy price to determine a hosting edge cost

model (Section 6.1). To ensure a good trade-off between our deployment approach generalization and its application to specific MNO's topologies, we contrast our latency model with large-scale measurements on a mobile network in the UK (Section 5.2), to further adjust the value ranges for the latency components.

- We evaluate our multi-tier MEC architecture using a real network topology with actual usage demands collected from the mobile network in the UK (Section 7). Our results highlight the benefits of deploying a 3-tier MEC architecture rather than single-tier solutions, in terms of cost and energy, as well as the importance of considering service characteristics since the initial MEC deployment. We also show that, while a centralized MEC deployment is cost-efficient for low-demand services, a distributed deployment is more suitable for high-demand services. Therefore, a multi-tier architecture is a scalable cost-efficient solution for heterogeneous services, decreasing costs by 56% and 48% compared to distributed and centralized solutions, respectively.

2. Related work

Despite the increasing interest in edge computing and MEC, several open questions remain, for example, related to the optimal placement and configuration of edge servers in a mobile network. In this respect, the work in [43] analyzed the trade-off between latency requirements and the use of cloud computing versus MEC deployments through simulations, providing the basis for showing the benefits of multi-tier MEC deployments.

Although MEC placement and MEC configuration are coupled problems, only a few works took both into consideration (e.g., [29]). The placement problem, involving the selection of optimal edge locations (e.g., cloudlets [44,45]), received relatively more attention, with most of the work focusing on reducing latency without considering costs [24,25,30,32,33,39,45–49]. However, to achieve an efficient deployment of edge servers in 5G/B5G networks, it is key to take deployment and operational costs into account, which were not considered in the aforementioned works. Other works focused instead on cost-aware deployment strategies [50], aiming to find a balance between cost reduction and latency minimization [31,34,41], while considering server capacity [51,52] or reliability [53].

Some work analyzed MEC placement and/or configuration by specifically focusing on vehicular services. The work in [28,38] proposed to place edge servers alongside roadside units (RSUs) and defined a multi-objective function to minimize latency while maximizing workload balance. The work in [26] considered vehicle mobility for solving the edge placement, while the work in [23] formulated the optimization problem to maximize and balance the data processed by edge servers. The authors of [27] discussed a multi-tier MEC deployment at RSUs, Macro Base Stations (MBSs), and cloud sites, and solved it via heuristics, preliminary highlighting the benefits of a multi-tier MEC architecture for vehicular services.

The above research did not analyze how service heterogeneity impacts MEC deployment strategies. In this paper, we instead include the characteristics of different C-V2X services in the MEC deployment optimization problem. To meet C-V2X service demands, we then propose a multi-tier MEC architecture in line with 3GPP specifications on NG-RAN disaggregated architectures. Another primary goal for our work is to use realistic characteristics, requirements, and configuration values for the different elements of the optimization problem, e.g., server cost and capacity, end-to-end latency models, and network topology and usage. Therefore, we derive a latency model that takes into account multiple communication and computation latency contributions. The use of this model sets our paper apart from most previous studies, where latency was simplistically modeled as a function of the Euclidean distance between users and servers (e.g., [14,26,32,41]).

As regards to network topology and usage, we leverage the physical nationwide network architecture of an MNO in the UK, as well as,

Table 1
Comparative analysis against other work on Edge/MEC deployment (placement and/or configuration). *d/e* stand for Deployment/Energy cost.

	Vehicular services	Multi-tier MEC	MEC configuration	Service heterogeneity	Disaggregated NG-RAN	Cost objective	Cellular network	Real-world network setup
[26]	✓					<i>d</i>		Taxi-2007 [36]
[27]	✓	✓	✓			<i>d</i>	✓	Simulations
[23]	✓					<i>d</i>		RSU-2014 [37]
[38]	✓							RSU-2014 [37]
[28]	✓							RSU-2014 [37]
[30]			✓				✓	MNO-2020
[39]			✓				✓	MNO-2014 [40]
[41]			✓	✓		<i>d</i>		WiFi-2019 [42]
[29]			✓			<i>d, e</i>	✓	MNO-2014 [40]
[31]			✓			<i>d</i>	✓	MNO-2014 [40]
This paper	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	<i>d, e</i>	✓	National MNO-2023

Fig. 2. High-level view of the measurement infrastructure.

up-to-date information on car connectivity for this network, aiming to provide grounded insights in contrast to previous studies that often relied on simulations or outdated data, e.g., for WiFi [42,54], mobile networks [40,55], and ad-hoc public transportation networks [37,56]. Among the work on edge deployment examined in this section, Table 1 summarizes the papers most relevant to our work, to further highlight our contribution.

3. Dataset

We collected the dataset used in this paper from the network of a large MNO with more than 30 million users in the UK. Fig. 2 depicts a high-level view of the measurement infrastructure deployed on the MNO’s architecture, used to collect our dataset. In particular, we monitored the elements marked with red pins: Mobility Management Entity (MME), Message Sequence Chart (MSC), Serving GPRS Support Node (SGSN), Serving Gateway (SGW), and the radio base stations. We further detail in this section the collected data.

Cell sites. We collected a daily snapshot of the radio network topology to capture the network deployment. From the topology, we then extracted the cell sites, which represent the locations where the MNO deploys its base stations (i.e., radio antennas and RAN elements). The MNO under study has more than 80,000 cell sites deployed in the UK.

Mobility management control data (MME). The MNO captures user activity in the control plane, for each supported Radio Access Technology (RAT). Each event carries the anonymized user ID, International Mobile Equipment Identity (IMEI), the radio base station ID handling

Fig. 3. Dataset representativity: Comparison between MNO client population and total UK population (left); Car distribution in the UK over a 10 km grid (right).

the communication, timestamps, etc. We used this data to find the number of devices per second.

Users Catalog. The MNO further collects and processes MME data to keep a high-level daily view of active users for long-term analyses. It includes the IMEI and overall statistics per day, such as used RAT, the connection time spent, mobility metrics, etc. In this paper, we used the *bounding box diagonal* of the space covered by a user [57] and the *entropy*. Entropy measures the randomness of users’ movements and thus implies the repeatability of movements [58]. We implemented a temporal uncorrelated entropy [58] based on the fraction of the time users spent in each visited base station.

Identifying cars. From the total population of devices connected to the MNO’s network, we identified connected cars and smartphones. To do so, we used a heuristic method based on (1) device type obtained from Global System for Mobile communications Association (GSMA) Type Allocation Code (TAC) database and (2) Access Point Name (APN) strings providing information about the IoT vertical. For example, through our method, we can infer that devices with *vehicle* device type are cars, and devices using *tesla.m2 m.gprs* APN are equipment installed in Tesla cars. Although we are aware of the limitations of our method, we discovered roughly one million cars daily by using it. Given that over 70% of users in our dataset are identified with the APN, and we include all well-known car brands in our classification, we are confident in the adequacy of our data. However, we plan to apply a more systematic method in future analyses, considering the growing number of cars and heterogeneity of vehicular services [35].

Dataset representativity. An inherent limitation of our work is that it is influenced by the MNO’s market share, and how this latter reflects the general population. To validate its reliability, we assigned all MNO’s clients to a Local Authority District (LAD) [59] based on their home postcode, and compared with values of estimated population from the Office for National Statistics. As shown in Fig. 3 (left), we found a

Table 2

Characteristics and requirements of the C-V2X services used in this paper. T_s denotes the inter-packet arrival time [ms], J_s^{\max} is the latency requirement [ms], and p_s is the packet size [Bytes] [35,63–65]. In the last column, we report relevant work highlighting the benefits of using MEC towards satisfying the requirements of each service class.

	T_s	p_s	J_s^{\max}	Service examples	Examples of MEC usage
Service 1	100	Pattern of {300, 190, 190, 190, 190} B	100	Roadwork warning, infotainment, parking access	[66–69]
Service 2	10	1200 B with probability of 0.2 and 800 B with probability of 0.8	10	Collision avoidance, vehicle platooning	[70–72]
Service 3	30	Randomly between 30000 B and 60000 B with a quantization step of 10000	30	Extended sensors, remote driving, automated driving	[73–75]

Fig. 4. The evolution of the number of cars connected to a mobile network (left), and of their connection capability (right), over the last three years.

Fig. 5. Mobility behavior of connected cars and smartphones: connection time to the top base stations (left) and bounding box diagonal (middle) indicate limited user movement within a small area, while the entropy (right) suggests higher movement predictability for cars.

strong linear relationship between the two variables ($r^2 = 0.941$, in line with the literature [60]), which validates the representativity of our dataset. We also observed that major MNOs have similar infrastructure and coverage in the UK [61,62].

In Fig. 3 (right), we show the distribution of cars throughout the UK. We compute the location of each car based on the location of its top base station, where the car connects most of the time during a day. The figure highlights a widespread distribution of cars across the entire country and also shows an uneven geographic spread with higher car densities in major cities like London. This is inline with the distribution of aggregated mobile data traffic from all UK MNOs published by Ofcom in [4] (Fig. 6 in the document). The results confirm again the representativity and scale of our dataset and also the necessity to deploy a nation-wide MEC platform to meet national vehicular service demands.

4. Vehicular services

C-V2X services are key use cases for 5G/B5G mobile networks, with connected cars increasingly using mobile networks [4,6,76]. In this section, we use our dataset to characterize the service demand evolution from the cars in the MNO’s network under study.

4.1. Car evolution

We explore the long-term trends for the number of cars using mobile network connectivity and for the evolution in the car connection capability from 2G to 5G. Fig. 4 (left) shows the number of cars connected to the MNO’s network in 2020, 2022, and 2023, for the first day of every month we have data available.¹ We find that the number of cars increased by 7.5x from 2020 to 2022, and by 13% from 2022 to 2023. Since 2022, there are more than one million cars connected daily. This confirms the high growth rate anticipated by GSMA [76]. Considering 41 million cars licensed in the UK at the end of December 2022 [77] and the market share of the MNO under analysis, we reasonably expect that the upward trend will continue. According to our model, we expect 1.35 million cars on the MNO’s network by the end of 2024. Fig. 4 (right) shows that, from 2020 to 2022, cars are swiftly migrating their connection capability from 2G to 4G technologies, with 4G-capable cars being predominant at the time of writing. Although only a tiny fraction of cars (i.e., 0.08%) are 5G-capable today, the technological trend anticipates a growing support for 5G. Hence, it is crucial to optimize 5G/B5G networks and MEC architectures towards meeting the demands of next-generation cars and C-V2X services.

4.2. Car mobility patterns

We also use our dataset to observe the mobility behavior of cars, and derive realistic requirements for edge computing architectures to support vehicular services. Therefore, we analyze how cars daily connect to different base stations to discern their mobility patterns from smartphones, which are the main service customers of mobile networks as of today. We use data from Week 7 in 2023 for this analysis.

Fig. 5 (left) shows in a boxplot format the percentage of time that connected cars and smartphones spend on the top 5 and top 20 base stations they use during a day (top5 and top20 in the figure).² Although we would expect high car mobility, we observe that 93% of cars connect to only 5 base stations for more than 80% of their connection time. This confirms a well-known human behavior of connecting to a few hot-spots (e.g., near to houses and workplaces), which is also true for smartphones [78]. Similar conclusions can be derived by observing the top20 distribution, with shorter boxes implying that smartphones and cars mostly connect to the top 20 base stations.

Fig. 5 (middle) shows the maximum distance between the top base stations, i.e., the bounding box diagonal that cars travel during a day (bbdiagonal) [57]. We observe that both cars and smartphones move in relatively small areas, with the 75-th percentile of bbdiagonal being 20 km for cars and 12 km for smartphones when we consider top5 base stations. The same applies when we consider the entire area covered by users, denoted as overall in Fig. 5 (middle). Moreover, although cars connect longer to their top5 base stations, the median

¹ No data available for 2021.

² We show boxplots with whiskers of 1.5 times the interquartile range.

Fig. 6. MEC deployment in our 3-tier MEC solution: Tier-1 – MEC at Core (green), Tier-2 – MEC at CU (yellow), and Tier-3 – MEC at DU (blue). The communication latency components for each tier are also shown (see latency model in Section 5.2). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of bbdiagonal for them is almost twice compared to smartphones (i.e., 11.1 km vs. 5 km), ultimately confirming that cars are more mobile than smartphones. Fig. 5 (right) shows that the median of the entropy for cars is 26% lower than that of smartphones, suggesting that the spatial movement of cars, despite covering larger areas, is more predictable than the movement of smartphones.

Based on the available data, we observe that car mobility is concentrated in relatively small areas. Therefore, edge computing can help concentrate data traffic and processing from future vehicular services (Intel estimates 4 TB per day of data traffic for an autonomous car [79]), ultimately reducing backhaul load and congestion.

4.3. Incentives for using multi-tier MEC

The 5GAA, which includes members from both telco (e.g., AT&T, Ericsson, NOKIA) and automotive industry sectors (e.g., Audi, BMW, Ford), identified several use cases from vehicle management to autonomous driving, thus envisioning a new ecosystem where cars are connected to the mobile network for both safety and non-safety use cases [64]. Along with ETSI [20], they envisioned MEC support specifically for C-V2X services, considering that the majority of these services are latency-critical and thus they cannot be supported only via cloud-based solutions [80,81]. For instance, MEC is used for collision avoidance [71,72], traffic safety enhancement [68], real-time traffic surveillance and processing [66,69], information exchange between vulnerable road users and vehicles [72,82,83], traffic congestion avoidance [67], cooperative adaptive driving [70], video streaming of vehicle camera sensors [84], and autonomous driving [73–75]. In this context, industries already blur the line between the edge and the cloud, with solutions that create a cloud–edge continuum, e.g., on-premises private cloud [85,86]. These solutions need to cater to services with significantly different demands. For instance, while automatic driving tolerates a maximum latency of 3 ms, assisted driving demands latency from 20 to 100 ms [87]. Therefore, we argue that a multi-tier MEC deployment can satisfy the heterogeneous requirements of vehicular services [8,88] while considering service coverage and deployment/energy costs. As we further detail in Section 5.2 also using our real-world measurements, the transport latency between base stations and MEC nodes can occasionally reach as high as 10 ms, failing to meet the latency demand of latency-critical services, even without considering other latency components.

To validate our proposal of a multi-tier MEC architecture, we adopt the three service models in [63], which reflect the diversity of vehicular services. Service 1 is representative of low traffic, Service 3 is representative of high traffic and Service 2 represents ultra-low latency services. The traffic characteristics, latency requirements, and real-world use cases for these services are reported in Table 2. In the table

and in the following, the one-way latency budget for a service s is denoted l_s^{\max} [ms]. Note that for services such as vehicle platooning, roadwork warning, parking access – which may utilize vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I), vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V), or vehicle-to-pedestrian (V2P) communications – MEC deployments remain beneficial, as also reported in [89]. For example, the work in [70] showed that MEC can improve the stability of vehicle platooning. Furthermore, MEC servers can support the transmission of messages containing V2I, V2V, V2P application information to one or more users (i.e., in applications such as vehicle platooning, roadwork warning, and parking access) [89].

5. Proposed architecture and latency model

This section describes our proposed multi-tier MEC architecture and how it aligns with NG-RAN design. Then, it details the latency model we derive for providing realistic evaluations of different MEC deployment strategies.

5.1. Multi-tier MEC architecture

Depending on service requirements and deployment/energy costs, MNOs may choose to deploy MEC instances at different sites in their mobile networks, likely co-located with the existing infrastructure to reduce the capital expenditure (e.g., rental costs) [90]. For example, as detailed in [91], MEC instances could be deployed at antenna sites, transmission nodes, network aggregation points, and in the core network (hereafter “Core”).

In the RAN context, 3GPP recently introduced the concept of NG-RAN *disaggregation* to enhance RAN efficiency [22]. The disaggregated NG-RAN enables a split of RAN functions across different elements, referred to as Radio Units (RUs), Distributed Units (DUs), and Central Units (CUs), potentially deployed at different locations. Among different split options, *Option 2* (co-located RU/DU and distant CU, for centralized processing) and *Option 6* (RU and closely co-located DU/CU, for distributed processing) are envisioned as NG-RAN reference implementations, with their coexistence made possible by Network Function Virtualization (NFV). In our multi-tier MEC architecture, we thus consider these two options, for which we provide some more background in Appendix A.1.

Considering a 5G/B5G network with disaggregated NG-RAN, we propose to map possible MEC deployment locations with the physical locations of Core instances, as well as with the physical locations where DUs and CUs are deployed, depending on the split option. We thus make the following assumptions and definitions:

Core locations. The locations hosting Core instances.

CU locations. If not co-located with DUs (as in Option 6), CUs are deployed at locations relatively distant from antenna sites and central offices. Therefore, we assume CUs deployed in so-called network aggregation points [91].

DU locations. If not located with RUs (as in Option 2), DUs are deployed at central offices close to antenna sites.

With the above definitions and assumptions, we propose a 3-tier MEC architecture with three main MEC deployment tiers, as depicted in Fig. 6:

- **Tier-1:** MEC deployed at Core locations.
- **Tier-2:** MEC deployed at locations where CUs are deployed (as made possible by Option 2)
- **Tier-3:** MEC deployed at locations where DUs and CUs are deployed together (as made possible by Option 6).

To ensure user plane functionalities, we assume User Plane Function (UPF) instances located with MEC instances, which is possible via Control User Plane Separation (CUPS) and Local Breakout (LBO) [92, 93]. Considering the operational and maintenance costs [94], security

concerns [90,95], and the small latency gains of deploying MEC at RUs compared to a Tier-3 MEC [96], we argue that the our 3-tier architecture is a reasonable approach, and another tier at RUs is not necessary.

5.2. Latency model

To provide a realistic evaluation of MEC architectures and deployment strategies, we propose a latency model that accounts for multiple factors. In particular, we model the one-way uplink latency, considering that uplink transmissions are more critical than the downlink for several C-V2X services [97–99].

Assuming a User Equipment (UE) connected to RU r and requesting a service s from a MEC instance m , the latency experienced by this UE — $l_{r,s,m}$ — is the sum of the communication latency over the link between user and MEC — $l_{r,s,m}^{\text{comm}}$ — and the computation latency of the MEC instance — $l_{s,m}^{\text{mec}}$ —, i.e., $l_{r,s,m} = l_{r,s,m}^{\text{comm}} + l_{s,m}^{\text{mec}}$.

The term $l_{r,s,m}^{\text{comm}}$ includes the following components:

- l^{ue} : packet processing latency at the UE;
- l_s^{air} : over-the-air latency between UE and RU, which depends on the packet size of service s ;
- $l_s^{\text{ts, fh}}$ and $l_s^{\text{tx, fh}}$: fronthaul (FH) transport (ts) latency and transmission (tx) latency over the RU-DU links;
- $l_s^{\text{ts, mh}}$ and $l_s^{\text{tx, mh}}$: midhaul (MH) transport (ts) latency and transmission (tx) latency over the DU-CU links;
- $l_s^{\text{ts, bh}}$ and $l_s^{\text{tx, bh}}$: backhaul (BH) transport (ts) latency and transmission (tx) latency over the CU-Core links. Note that we always assume the transport latency independent of the service while the transmission latency is service-dependent (we expand on this later in the section);
- l^{ru} , l^{du} , l^{cu} , l^{core} : latency at the RU, DU, CU, and Core nodes.

Fig. 6 shows a color-coded illustration of the $l_{r,s,m}^{\text{comm}}$ components, based on possible MEC deployment tiers. It is worth highlighting that our model applies to all MEC deployment tiers, but some of the components are zero for specific MEC locations. For example, $l_s^{\text{ts, mh}}$, $l_s^{\text{tx, mh}}$, $l_s^{\text{ts, bh}}$, $l_s^{\text{tx, bh}}$, l^{cu} , and l^{core} are zero for MEC deployed at Tier-3.

We now provide more details on each latency component. Specifically, we run an extensive review of the state of the art as well as large-scale measurements on a production mobile network to find the correct value ranges to the latency components introduced above. In the following, we focus on major latency components, deferring the analysis of negligible components to Appendix A.2.

Over-the-air latency — l_s^{air} .

To compute l_s^{air} , we calculate the number of transport blocks (TBs)/ slots needed to transmit an application packet for the services in Table 2, as a function of the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) — an index between 0 and 27 for selecting modulation order and coding scheme used for the TBs — and the number of physical resource blocks (PRBs) allocated to a user, considering 30 kHz Subcarrier Spacing (SCS) and thus a slot duration of 0.5 ms [100]. Assuming a typical 10% target block error rate (BLER) [101], we also simulate hybrid automatic repeat request (HARQ) retransmissions by considering a total amount of transmitted data 10% greater than the data actually generated by the UE. We also assume the use of (a) a Time Division Duplex (TDD) pattern equal to DDDSU [102], where D stands for a downlink slot, S is for a special slot for both downlink/uplink transmissions (with 10:2 ratio), and U stands for an uplink slot, and (b) minislot transmissions for small latency-sensitive packets (as for our C-V2X services) [103], so that such packets can be transmitted in the second half of U slots if they are generated during the first half.

With these assumptions, we calculate that 1 TB (slot) is enough for transmitting packets of Services 1 and 2 in Table 2, regardless of MCS and PRB allocations. According to [102], the maximum latency for URLLC for the transmission of 1 TB is 2.25 ms. Hence, l_s^{air} ranges from

Fig. 7. Transport latency measurements and estimation.

0.25 ms (due to minislot transmissions) to 2.25 ms for these services. For Service 3, up to 6 TBs may be needed for cars getting at least 20 MHz bandwidth in medium/good channel conditions (MCS \geq 10). In this case, l_s^{air} is between 0.25 ms and $6 \cdot 2.25 = 13.5$ ms.

FH, MH, BH Transport latency — $l_s^{\text{ts, fh}}$, $l_s^{\text{ts, mh}}$, $l_s^{\text{ts, bh}}$. The transport latency is the signal propagation time over FH, MH, and BH links. It is thus a function of the link length and the signal propagation speed on the link, which in turn depends on the link nature (e.g., fiber, coaxial cable, or wireless link). In order to realistically model this latency component, instead of calculating it as $\frac{\text{distance}}{\text{speed of light}}$ [39,104], we leverage real-world traces by the MNO under study and use a linear regression to account for the impact of the distance between network nodes. Fig. 7 shows the regression curve we fit to the data samples collected in the MNO's network. We thus derive the following model: $l_s^{\text{ts, x}} = 0.014 \cdot \text{distance}_x + 1.225$, where $x = [\text{fh, mh, bh}]$ and distance_x is the link length (i.e., the distance between RU-DU, DU-CU and CU-Core [km]).

FH, MH, BH Transmission latency — $l_s^{\text{tx, fh}}$, $l_s^{\text{tx, mh}}$, $l_s^{\text{tx, bh}}$. The transmission latency is the time it takes to transmit an application packet onto the physical medium. Hence, it depends on the packet size for service s (i.e., p_s in bits), and the link transmission rate R_x , where $x = [\text{fh, mh, bh}]$, so that $l_s^{\text{tx, x}} = \frac{p_s}{R_x}$ [104,105]. According to [106], we consider $R_{\text{fh}} = 10$ Gb/s, $R_{\text{mh}} = 25$ Gb/s, and $R_{\text{bh}} = 100$ Gb/s.

MEC computation latency — $l_{s,m}^{\text{mec}}$. This component depends on the MEC computation capability and the received task. Assuming that a user has a computational task of b bits, and that cl CPU cycles are needed to process one bit, we use the widely used formula $\frac{b \cdot cl}{cc}$ to evaluate the task computation latency, where cc is the server computational capability (e.g., [82,107–110]). The MEC computation latency for cars requesting service s from MEC m is evaluated as in Eq. (1):

$$l_{s,m}^{\text{mec}} = \frac{n_{s,m} \cdot p_s \cdot cl}{cc_m \cdot v_{s,m}}, \quad (1)$$

where $n_{s,m}$ is the number of cars requesting service s from MEC m and $v_{s,m}$ is the number of servers/processors deployed at MEC m for supporting service s .

For convenience, we summarize the variables of our latency model in Table 3.

6. Cost model and optimization

In this section, we first define our cost model. Then, on top of the multi-tier MEC architecture defined in the previous section, we formulate the multi-tier MEC deployment strategy, denoted as *MT-MEC*, as an optimization problem that considers both cost and service requirements.

Table 3
Summary of notation used in latency and cost models, and in the optimization problem..

Notation	Definition
$s \in S$	s th service in set S , with $ S = S$
T_s, p_s	Inter-packet arrival time and packet size of service s
$r \in \mathcal{R}$	r th RU in set \mathcal{R} , with $ \mathcal{R} = R$
$m \in \mathcal{M}$	m th MEC instance/location in set \mathcal{M} , with $ \mathcal{M} = M$
Latency Model Components	
J_s^{\max}	Latency requirement of service s
$l_{r,s,m}$	End-to-end latency of cars at RU r requesting service s from MEC m
$J_{r,s,m}^{\text{comm}}$	95-quantile of communication latency of cars at RU r requesting service s from MEC m
$J_{s,m}^{\text{mec}}$	Computation latency of cars requesting service s from MEC m
J^{ue}	Packet processing latency at UE
J_s^{air}	Over-the-air latency between UE and RU
$J_{\text{fh}}^{\text{ts}}, J_{\text{fh}}^{\text{tx}}$	Transport (ts) and Transmission (tx) latencies over RU-DU fronthaul links
$J_{\text{mh}}^{\text{ts}}, J_{\text{mh}}^{\text{tx}}$	Transport (ts) and Transmission (tx) latencies over DU-CU midhaul links
$J_{\text{bh}}^{\text{ts}}, J_{\text{bh}}^{\text{tx}}$	Transport (ts) and Transmission (tx) latencies over CU-Core backhaul links
$J_r^{\text{ru}}, J_r^{\text{du}}$	Latency at RU and DU nodes
$J_c^{\text{cu}}, J_c^{\text{core}}$	Latency at CU and Core nodes
$n_{s,m}$	Decision variable denoting the number of cars requesting service s at MEC m
$u_{s,m}$	Decision variable denoting the number of servers deployed at MEC m for service s
cc_m	Computation capability of a server at MEC m
cl	CPU cycles for processing one bit
Cost Model Components	
C_m	Computational cost of MEC m
D_m	Deployment cost of MEC m
w	Scaling factor to balance energy and deployment costs
E_m	Energy cost of MEC m
tdp_m	Thermal design power of a CPU at MEC m
t	Time horizon
ep	Electricity price
F_m	Operating cost of MEC m
Optimization Problem Variables	
$\text{map}_{r,m}$	Binary variable equal to 1 if RU r and MEC m can be linked (network topology)
C_s	Total number of cars requesting service s
$z_{r,s,m}$	Binary variable denoting at least one car at RU r requests service s from MEC m
V_m^{\max}	Maximum number of servers that can be deployed at MEC m
K	Constant equal to $10 \cdot V_m^{\max}$
y_m	Binary variable indicating at least one server deployed at MEC m
$n_{r,s,m}$	Decision variable denoting the number of cars at RU r requesting service s from MEC m
$C_{r,s}$	Total number of cars connected to RU r requesting service s

6.1. Cost model

To frame a MEC deployment optimization problem, we consider both operating costs of a MEC platform once deployed (e.g., rent), denoted as F_m , and the MEC computational cost, denoted as C_m . Regarding F_m , we assume a co-location hosting model, wherein a server can be located within a leased physical area provided by a hosting company [111]. This approach allows for the MNO to have a single cost and avoid the operational costs and challenges associated with maintaining data centers, such as cooling, and security.

We model C_m as the sum of two components, *deployment cost* (D_m) and *energy cost* (E_m), as follows:

$$C_m = D_m + w \cdot E_m, \quad (2)$$

where the scaling factor $w > 0$ balances the importance of energy costs over deployment costs.

We define the deployment cost D_m as the cost of purchasing the servers/processors needed to run a MEC instance, based on actual

prices from manufacturers (Intel in our case, see Table 4). We define the energy cost E_m as the processors' long-term static energy consumption. We believe this provides a reliable estimate since the CPU power constitutes a significant share in the energy consumption [112,113], and we assume that processors are always ON (even when in idle state, they consume about 30% of their peak power [114,115]). Therefore, we take the thermal design power (TDP) from manufacturer's specifications (Intel in our case, see Table 4) as a long-term indicator of CPU power [116,117]. We denote the TDP for MEC instance m as tdp_m (e.g., in kilowatt) and multiply it by the time t an MNO may want to account for energy costs in advance (e.g., in hours). A longer t implies a longer horizon, allowing the MNO to plan further into the future while initially deploying its MEC platform. In Eq. (3), we compute E_m by multiplying the energy consumption over time by the electricity price ep (e.g., dollars per kilowatt-hour):

$$E_m = tdp_m \cdot t \cdot ep. \quad (3)$$

Eq. (4) shows how we compute the total cost, as a function of supported services and deployed MEC instances (i.e., the outcome of

the optimization problem in Section 6.2):

$$\text{Total Cost} = \sum_m F_m \cdot t \cdot y_m + \sum_m \sum_s C_m \cdot v_{s,m}. \quad (4)$$

The cost F_m is also considered over t , the unit of which is modified depending on the unit of F_m (e.g., dollars per month). Moreover, y_m is a binary variable equal to 1 if there is a MEC instance at location m , and $v_{s,m}$ is as in Eq. (1).

For convenience, we summarize the variables of our cost model in Table 3.

6.2. Optimization problem

We define the set of RUs as $\{r_1, \dots, r_R\} \in \mathcal{R}$, the set of MEC candidate locations as $\{m_1, \dots, m_M\} \in \mathcal{M}$, and the set of services as $\{s_1, \dots, s_S\} \in \mathcal{S}$. Moreover, C_s represents the total number of cars requesting service s , while $C_{r,s}$ is the number of cars connected to the RU r that request service s . We aim at finding an optimal MEC deployment strategy such that the total cost in Eq. (4) is minimized, while the latency demand for all cars requesting services $s \in \mathcal{S}$ are met.

We formulate the optimization problem as follows:

$$\text{Min [Total Cost]} \quad (5)$$

subject to:

$$l_{r,s,m} \cdot \text{map}_{r,m} \cdot z_{r,s,m} \leq l_s^{\max}, \quad \forall r, s, m \quad (6)$$

$$n_{r,s,m} - C_s \cdot z_{r,s,m} \leq 0, \quad \forall r, s, m \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_s v_{s,m} - K \cdot y_m \leq 0, \quad \forall m \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_s v_{s,m} \leq V_m^{\max}, \quad \forall m \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_m n_{r,s,m} \cdot \text{map}_{r,m} = C_{r,s}, \quad \forall r, s \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_m n_{s,m} = C_s, \quad \forall s \quad (11)$$

$$0 \leq v_{s,m} \leq V_m^{\max}, \quad \forall s, m \quad (12)$$

$$n_{r,s,m} \geq 0, \quad \forall r, s, m \quad (13)$$

$$z_{r,s,m} = \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall r, s, m \quad (14)$$

$$n_{s,m} = \sum_r n_{r,s,m}, \quad \forall s, m \quad (15)$$

$$y_m = \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall m \quad (16)$$

Eq. (5) represents the optimization objective, while Eq. (6) expresses the latency constraint, which we assume satisfied if the experienced latency $l_{r,s,m}$ is lower than the latency budget l_s^{\max} for the requested service s . The variable $\text{map}_{r,m}$ is a component of a binary matrix having dimensions $R \times M$, and it is 1 if the RU r has a direct link with the m th candidate MEC location. This depends on the MNO's network topology, as further explained in Section 7.1. The latency constraint in Eq. (6) is evaluated only if there is at least one car connected to RU r requesting service s from MEC m , which would make the binary variable $z_{r,s,m}$ be equal to 1. This is enforced via Eq. (7), where $n_{r,s,m}$ is a variable representing the number of cars connected to RU r and requesting service s from MEC location m . Similarly, the constraint in Eq. (8) links $v_{s,m}$ with y_m (see Section 6.1), so that the fixed operating cost F_m in Eq. (4) is considered if at least one server is deployed at MEC location m . Here, K is a big number, at least equal to a maximum number of servers that can be deployed at MEC location m , i.e., V_m^{\max} , which we set to $10 \cdot V_m^{\max}$.

Eq. (9) specifies the maximum number of servers that can be placed in a particular MEC location m . This constraint applies per location, not per MEC tier, thus MEC instances at one tier (e.g., Tier-1) may have different capacities regarding the number of servers they can

Table 4

Experimental setup for each MEC location, including the configuration and price of servers/processors (Intel Xeon series). Prices (D_m & F_m [121]) are in \$, cc_m in GHz, and tdp_m in Watts. See Section 6.1 and 6.2 for a definition of each variable.

MEC tier	CPU model	cc_m	tdp_m	D_m	F_m	V_m^{\max}
1	8470 [122]	187	300	9520	200	220
2	8462Y+ [123]	131	300	5945	100	150
3	4416+ [124]	78	165	1176	50	50

deploy. Eqs. (10) and (11) guarantee that all cars requesting services will be served by one MEC instance only. Eq. (10) further indicates that a car can connect to one MEC instance, if it has a link to it via the RU it is connected to. The last five constraints in Eqs. (12)–(16) limit the intervals over which the decision variables can change. For convenience, we summarize the variables of our optimization problem in Table 3.

6.3. Solving the optimization problem

As observed in [25,27,46,52], the placement of computing nodes at the network edge problem is NP-hard, and it can be seen as a capacitated facility location problem (i.e., a combinatorial optimization problem to determine the number and locations of a set of facilities and assign customers to them while minimizing costs [118,119]).

In our setup, we observe that it is not necessary to find the optimal MEC placement and configuration for all the locations at the same time; we can instead divide the entire problem into sub-problems to be solved for each Core locations independently. This split allows us to find an optimal solution using the Gurobi solver [120], as it significantly reduces the number of RUs and MEC locations that the solver needs to consider. In addition, the optimization problem is not dependent on the number of cars and scales solely with the number of RUs, typically in the range of thousands, as opposed to the significantly larger number of cars, which reaches into the millions. We further enhance the solver efficiency by leveraging Gurobi's *lazy constraints*. Lazy constraints remain inactive until a feasible solution is discovered. Once a solution is found, it is checked against the lazy constraint pool and discarded if violates any constraints. We use this feature instead of the decision variable $z_{r,s,m}$ to limit the latency only when $n_{r,s,m}$ is greater than 1. This reduces the number of constraints (Gurobi considers the latency constraints only when necessary), and makes the problem scalable through the elimination of the $z_{r,s,m}$ variable.

7. Performance evaluation

This section presents the experimental setup, baseline strategies, and the evaluation results.

7.1. Experimental setup

In order to analyze the performance of our *MT-MEC* deployment strategy under realistic settings, we use the network infrastructure of the MNO under study. In particular, we consider the current antenna sites as RUs, the central offices as DUs (approximately one every 20 km), network aggregation points as CUs, and the data centers hosting 4G/5G Cores as Core locations. With respect to the number of RUs, the MNO's network has 3.5% DUs, 0.08% CUs, and 0.04% Core locations. We observe that all the network aggregation points are at a distance of less than 400 km from at least one Core instance, and the majority of central offices are within 200 km from at least one network aggregation point. These distances align with the ones envisioned by the O-RAN Alliance [88] (i.e., at most 20 km between RUs and DUs, 200 km between DUs and CUs, and 2000 km between CUs and Core), thus confirming the validity of our network mapping. We further discuss network topology aspects in Section 7.4.4, where the results obtained

Fig. 8. Performance for different MEC deployment strategies. *MT-MEC* outperforms all other strategies in terms of both deployment and energy costs. The error bars represent the standard deviation over five optimizations. The vertical gray lines in (e) and (f) indicate latency requirements. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

for the specific MNO's network topology are generalized and validated by assuming a more generic topology that also follows O-RAN guidelines. Therefore, apart for Section 7.4.4, we consider a static mapping between network nodes according to the MNO's network topology: an RU exclusively connects to a specific DU, CU, and Core and thus cars connected to it can only be allocated to MEC instances at these locations. The mapping results in the mapping matrix with elements $\text{map}_{r,m}$ (see Section 6.2), where at each r th row, there are three columns marked as 1, representing MEC potential locations at the corresponding DU, CU, and Core.

We quantify the service demand of cars based on the number of cars connected at each base station per second (see Section 3), and then compute daily percentiles (e.g., median, 90%, 95%, 100%). In the following, unless otherwise specified, we use the maximum number of cars (i.e., 100%) in our optimization problem. We always assume all cars request all three C-V2X services to thoroughly assess the impact of the various service demands on MEC deployment strategies and evaluate *MT-MEC* in the most demanding scenario.

Table 4 reports the other considered settings. With regards to the servers/processors for each MEC tier, we use the values suggested by Intel for IoT edge applications in terms of c_m , tdp_m , and deployment cost D_m [125]. Moreover, we assume cl uniformly distributed between 100 and 300 [82], t equal to 4 years, based on the estimated life long of processors in [126], and ep equal to 0.334 \$ per kWh, which is the average electricity price in the UK [127]. Finally, in Eq. (2), we always consider $w = 1$ except for Section 7.4.1, where we study the impact of different values for w .

7.2. Baseline strategies

In our evaluation, we compare the performance of *MT-MEC* against the following baseline strategies:

Single-tier MEC. Our goal in this paper is to quantify the performance improvements achievable by *MT-MEC* over single-tier deployment strategies. We thus evaluate optimal solutions using the Gurobi

solver for single-tier MEC strategies, denoted as *Tier-1*, *Tier-2*, and *Tier-3* strategies. *Tier-3* approximates the most popular approach in the literature, which considers MEC servers co-located with base stations [27,29]. In our setup, this would have been a single-tier strategy *Tier-4* as MEC co-located with RUs, which we however find extremely cost-inefficient and thus a non-viable option in realistic settings, as confirmed by the results we report in the next sections. As a further comparison, we also consider a 2-tier centralized deployment strategy, denoted as *Tier-1/2*, where we consider MEC instances at both *Tier-1* and *Tier-2*.

Heaviest First Algorithm (HAF) [29,45,52]. The idea behind the HAF strategy is to deploy MEC servers in hot-spot areas with the highest traffic. Initially, it sorts the candidate MEC locations based on the number of cars in the surrounding area. Then, in each iteration, it deploys MEC instances at the location with the most cars. Cars meeting their latency constraints are assigned to these MEC instances while ensuring compliance with the server capacity constraint. This process is iterative until all services requested by cars are fulfilled.

7.3. Cost and performance analysis

7.3.1. Cost

We start our analysis by evaluating the total cost of each MEC deployment strategy in Fig. 8(a). We observe that *MT-MEC* leads to the lowest cost, which is decreased by 56% compared to the *Tier-3* solution, 48% compared to *Tier-1*, and 48% compared to *HAF*. Furthermore, *Tier-3* is the most expensive approach in terms of both deployment and operating cost, which implies that a *Tier-3* MEC or at lower tiers (e.g., at RUs) is resource-inefficient. *Tier-1/2* and *Tier-2*, which are intermediary solutions, are the best options after *MT-MEC*.

To better understand the cost difference between strategies, we show the deployment cost D_m and energy cost E_m split across services in Fig. 8(b) and Fig. 8(c), respectively. The results indicate that *MT-MEC* leads to the minimum deployment and energy costs for all services. We

Table 5
The percentage of cars at each *MT-MEC* tier.

<i>MT-MEC</i> tier	Service		
	1	2	3
1	32	1	0
2	68	65	25
3	0	34	75

also observe that, for Service 1, more centralized approaches like *Tier-2* provide the minimum cost, whereas *Tier-3* results in high deployment and energy costs. On the other hand, for more demanding services (i.e., Service 3), *Tier-3* is a viable option in terms of deployment costs (Fig. 8(b)). Conversely, for centralized solutions, the reduction of computation latency to compensate for the increase of communication latency requires to add more servers, leading to a higher deployment cost.

Our analysis also reveals interesting trends in terms of energy costs. As we move towards more distributed MEC deployment strategies, energy costs significantly increase (Fig. 8(c)). For example, the energy cost for *Tier-3* accounts for 62% of the total cost, while it is 47% for *Tier-2* and 27% for *Tier-1*. This suggests to avoid distributed deployment strategies unless the targeted service demands for it (e.g., Service 2 and 3). *MT-MEC* leverages instead both centralized and distributed approaches by strategically assigning cars, as outlined in Table 5, to provide the most cost-effective deployment for all services. This approach strikes a balance between cost- and energy-efficiency. For Service 3, this results in a 28% reduction in energy costs compared to *Tier-3*, and a 29% and 3% reduction compared to *Tier-2* and *Tier-1*, and 4% compared to *HAF*, respectively.

With respect to service demands, we discovered that Service 3 has the highest cost although Service 2 is the most latency-demanding. This suggests that latency is not a complete indicator of service requirements. A service with a higher latency budget may still be more demanding due to higher data traffic and/or needs for more computational resources. Hence, both latency and data rate are necessary to estimate service demands.

To provide a complete picture of *MT-MEC* performance, we now present its effectiveness under various network traffic conditions. We categorize all Cores in the country into three categories: *low*, *medium*, and *high*, based on the number of cars connected to them. In particular, a Core is *low* if the number of cars per second connected to it is lower than 1000, *medium* if values are between 1000 and 1500, and *high* for more than 1500 connected cars. We then calculate the average total cost per Core for each category and present the results in Fig. 8(d). The observed pattern aligns with the total costs in Fig. 8(a), confirming that *MT-MEC* outperforms other deployment strategies across different traffic conditions.

7.3.2. Latency

We now assess the overall latency experienced by cars (i.e., $l_{r,s,m}$). The corresponding empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDFs) are reported in Fig. 8(e) for Service 2 and Fig. 8(f) for Service 3. Latency plots for Service 1 are excluded because all MEC deployment strategies meet the latency requirement for all cars, with a latency below 17 ms in all cases.

MT-MEC meets the latency demand of all services for all cars. On the other hand, *Tier-1* and *Tier-2* are not able to satisfy the latency demand of Service 2 for 3% and 0.5% of cars, respectively. Fig. 8(f) also shows that, with *MT-MEC*, 75% of cars achieve a latency lower than 26 ms for Service 3, leaving a 13% margin to the latency budget, which could be reused to satisfy future services with even more stringent requirements. This 75%-percentile is only 10% higher than *Tier-3*, which has however 56% higher costs.

Fig. 9. Energy optimization for *MT-MEC*. The scaling factor w balances deployment and energy costs. With an increasing w , the energy cost decreases but deployment and total costs increase (left). To reduce energy costs, the optimal deployment tends to be more centralized when $w \geq 1$ (right).

Fig. 10. *MT-MEC* cost percentage increment per service vs. SLO.

7.4. Sensitivity analysis

7.4.1. Energy consumption optimization

We now analyze the optimization process for *MT-MEC* with different scaling factors w , aiming to evaluate the impact of the trade-off between energy and deployment costs in Eq. (2). Fig. 9 (left) depicts the difference in total and energy cost for different values of w compared to the baseline scenario ($w = 1$). When w is 10, there is an 11.6% energy cost reduction. This translates into a decrease in energy consumption, which contributes to lower carbon emissions arising from electricity usage. However, to improve energy efficiency, the solution shifts towards a more centralized approach, as shown in Fig. 9 (right) for Service 2 (the same trend is observed for Service 3). This leads to an increase in deployment cost and, consequently, total cost. Conversely, reducing w to 0.1 leads to an increase in energy costs and, accordingly, total costs. With the integration of renewable energy sources, the energy costs may decrease [128], potentially diminishing its importance compared to deployment costs. In addition, deployment costs should be paid upfront, while the energy cost is a future expense. By adjusting w , an MNO can thus decide how to balance deployment and energy costs.

7.4.2. SLO guarantee cost

As a complementary analysis, we evaluate the cost of *MT-MEC* while guaranteeing different Service Level Objectives (SLOs) in this section. We start from the median number of cars and gradually increase to 90-th, 95-th, and 100-th percentiles. Fig. 10 shows the percentage increase in costs compared to the scenario of meeting the service demands of the median number of cars. We observe that, for Service 1, there is no cost increase to accommodate the demands of more cars. In contrast, the cost increases 47% for Service 2 and 53% for Service 3, when the median and 95th percentile are compared. This further emphasizes the importance of considering service demands and SLOs for setting up the initial MEC deployment plan. When we strive to satisfy the

Fig. 11. *MT-MEC* stability across future car growth: *MT-MEC* shows a low increase for overall cost (a) and cost per service (b).

maximum demand (denoted as Q100 in the figure), the cost increases to 3.5x for Service 2 and 2.3x for Service 3. The sharp increase for Service 2 is attributed to its latency budget (i.e., 10 ms), which requires more distributed MEC servers compared to providing demands for the median of cars. Also note that the plot depicts cost increments rather than absolute values, with the latter being always about 5x higher for Service 3 over Service 2.

7.4.3. Future growth

In Section 4.1, we highlighted a 13% increase in the number of cars over the past year. One can argue that, with the expected increase in the number of connected cars, the single-tier approaches could surpass *MT-MEC* in performance and efficiency in the future. To address scenarios with a higher car density, we thus conduct an experiment to factor in additional cars in the optimization. Fig. 11(a) shows the total cost of each strategy for different percentage increments in the number of connected cars. Note that we exclude the *HAF* scheme from this

analysis for two main reasons: (1) our primary focus is to compare *MT-MEC* against approaches with a lower number of tiers (1-tier and 2-tier schemes), and (2) *HAF* performance in the previous section already highlighted significant performance degradation of this scheme. With a 40% increase with respect to the current total number of cars, the cost of *MT-MEC* remains lower than the cost of the other strategies. Furthermore, the cost of *MT-MEC* increases at a 2% rate compared to the 8% for *Tier-1* and 5% for *Tier-1/2* and *Tier-2*. Only *Tier-3* grows at the same 2% rate.

An intriguing observation emerges at 40%: the total cost of *Tier-1* surpasses that of *Tier-3* by 11%. This is because, as we further show in Fig. 11(b), for Service 2, *Tier-1* necessitates a substantial increase of the computational capacity to reduce the computation latency and thus compensate for the large communication latency. Achieving this goal involves deploying several servers, and as the number of cars increases, the demand for a higher number of servers also rises, consequently escalating the costs. This suggests that for a scenario with a considerable number of cars (at least 25 cars per second per DU), the single-tier *Tier-3* MEC outperforms the centralized counterpart for the demanding Service 2.

Cost per service analysis shows that the cost for Service 1 remains constant for all MEC deployments, regardless of the car growth. In contrast, for Service 2, the cost increases by 10% for *MT-MEC* and approximately 20% for *Tier-2/Tier-1/2* with a 10% increase in the number of cars, stabilizing thereafter. On the contrary, the cost for *Tier-1* rises constantly by a rate of 0.02. For Service 3, the increase rate of cost for *Tier-1* is 0.06, for *Tier-1/2/Tier2* is 0.04, and for *MT-MEC/Tier-3* is 0.02. This emphasizes the impact of service demands on the optimal choice of MEC deployment. As the number of cars rises, the cost difference between *MT-MEC* and *Tier-3* for Service 3 decreases. For instance, the cost of *Tier-3* is 24% higher than that of *MT-MEC* for the current number of cars, while with a 40% increase, their margin reduces to 14%. This observation suggests that when the number of cars doubles from today's value, the cost of distributed approach *Tier-3* will align close with *MT-MEC* for Service 3. Therefore in scenarios with a high number of cars requiring demanding services in a small area, the *Tier-3* MEC will become inevitable.

7.4.4. O-RAN mapping

Finally, we evaluate our *MT-MEC* solution considering the mapping between network nodes proposed by the O-RAN Alliance. Hence, unlike the previous static mapping between RUs, DUs, and CUs, we now adopt the guidelines for maximum distances between network nodes in [88], aiming to generalize and further validate the results in earlier sections. For instance, considering that the O-RAN Alliance suggests a maximum distance between RU and DU of 20 km, we consider that each RU can be assigned to any DU within 20 km distance, and the same principle applies to CUs. In turn, this results in more than 3 MEC candidate locations per RU (i.e., this will change $map_{r,m}$ matrix to have more than 3 columns as 1 per row r). Fig. 12 shows that *MT-MEC* still achieves a lower cost compared to the other strategies (e.g., 44% and 60% lower costs compared to *Tier-3* and *Tier-1*, respectively).

7.5. Discussion

In this paper, we focus on C-V2X services, acknowledging that they are among the most demanding and challenging applications for 5G/B5G systems, ultimately requiring dedicated MEC support as also highlighted by the 3GPP, ETSI, and 5GAA (see Section 4.3). Hence, by addressing the stringent latency requirements of C-V2X services, MNOs can establish a robust foundation towards supporting services with more tolerant latency demands as well. Our results show notable benefits in applying *MT-MEC* instead of single-tier, less flexible deployment strategies for serving C-V2X services with heterogeneous characteristics and demands. A multi-tier MEC architecture is proven to be a preferable choice, not only in terms of deployment costs, but also with respect to

Fig. 12. *MT-MEC* adaptability: it outperforms other strategies considering general network topologies that follow O-RAN guidelines.

energy consumption. When providers only request services with less-demanding requirements, MNOs could satisfy the demand by using the centralized resources of multi-tier MEC (*MT-MEC*) (i.e., Tier-1 and/or Tier-2). If services with more-demanding requirements are also added, MNOs can employ the distributed resources of *MT-MEC* (i.e., Tier-3).

Our results also confirm substantial costs, reaching multi-million dollars, even with the current number of connected cars we observe in the MNO's network. When more cars will request C-V2X services, a higher computational capacity will be then needed at different MEC locations.

Finally, while our analysis considers user demand from a single MNO (albeit one of the largest in the UK), we argue that other MNOs have similar infrastructure and user demand patterns, with an overall increase of data traffic [129–131]. Therefore, individual deployments of MEC infrastructures by each MNO may not be a sustainable approach. Such a strategy could lead to inefficiencies and additional costs. This emphasizes the need for collaboration between MNOs and third-party cloud/edge providers to deploy sustainable MEC platforms for critical vehicular services. With the co-location hosting model we considered in Section 6.1, multiple operators can share the computation resources [132].

8. Conclusion

This paper examines the current status of connected cars on the cellular network from a major MNO's perspective, focusing on their demand for MEC deployment. In response, we propose a multi-tier MEC architecture aligned with the disaggregated NG-RAN, which we tailor to various characteristics and demands of vehicular services. We employ realistic settings and values for latency, cost, and network architecture. Later, we formulate the MEC deployment as an optimization problem that minimizes both initial deployment costs and future costs (including energy), while meeting C-V2X service requirements. We show that our *MT-MEC* approach outperforms the centralized/distributed single-tier architectures both in latency requirements – for all C-V2X services – and also in reducing the deployment and energy cost. Furthermore, our solution has persistent performance concerning future car growth.

As a future work, we plan to extend this work to an online user allocation under a dynamic network environment considering our *MT-MEC* deployment architecture. Other critical aspects of C-V2X services, such as mobility, reliability, security, and privacy considerations are also issues to be addressed in the future.

Ethical considerations

The data collected at network middle-boxes adheres to the MNO terms, local regulations, and Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs). All datasets are under strict confidentiality, with no re-sharing permitted. Raw data has been reviewed for General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, ensuring no identifying information. Data processing involves only aggregated user information, preventing access to personal details. This study does not involve user personal or contact information, and no data extraction or encryption was performed by the authors.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Paniz Parastar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giuseppe Caso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jesus Alberto Omaña Iglesias:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Andra Lutu:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Data curation. **Ozgu Alay:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Appendix

A.1. Disaggregated NG-RAN

The 5G/B5G NG-RAN may be formed by RUs, DUs, CUs. The RUs at the antenna sites are responsible for transmitting, amplifying, and digitizing radio signals; DUs are responsible for near real time low-layer functions at Physical (PHY) layer (with RUs) and Medium Access Control (MAC) and Radio Link Control (RLC) layers, and are thus either co-located with RUs or located in relatively close sites; CUs handle non-real time high-layer functions for Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) and Radio Resource Control (RRC) layers. If not co-located with DUs, CUs can be placed in data centers that are even more distant from antenna sites [133].

Compared to the monolithic RAN design of 4G networks, DUs are simpler and smaller than full-stack 4G base stations, as the higher-layer processing is taken over by the CUs. The functional split also facilitates RAN orchestration and potential energy savings, thanks to the possibility of a centralized control plane [134].

3GPP specifies different split options for implementing the disaggregated NG-RAN [22]. As shown in Fig. 13, we leverage for our work

Fig. 13. 5G network architecture as per 3GPP NG-RAN Option 2 (a) and Option 6 (b) functional splits [133].

the NG-RAN architectural deployments from two specific split options, i.e., Option 2 and Option 6. In the early stage of 5G/B5G network deployment, a high-layer split as Option 2 (Fig. 13(a)) is likely [133], with co-located RUs and DUs running PHY, MAC, and RLC layers, and distant CUs handling RRC and PDCP functions for one or more sets of RUs/DUs. As with regards to low-layer splits, discussions are still ongoing in standardization and industry fora. In particular, the Small Cell Forum supports Option 6 (Fig. 13(b)), with RUs handling the PHY layer, and DUs and CUs handling the rest of the protocol stack while being co-located in not too distant data centers; the O-RAN Alliance recommends instead a slightly different approach (referred to as Option 7.2 [135]), where the PHY layer is further divided in low-PHY (in RUs) and high-PHY (in DUs). In terms of MEC deployment, the difference between Options 6 and 7.2 likely has a minimal impact, therefore, we assume Option 6 along with Option 2 in this paper.

We observe that such split RAN strategies also align with the scenarios envisioned by the O-RAN Alliance, which suggests up to four tiers for deploying RAN and Core elements: RUs in the so-called Cell Site, DUs in the Edge Cloud, CUs in the Regional Cloud, and the Core in the Core Cloud [88]. Finally, we also highlight that we do not consider the non-split option (RUs, DUs, and CUs at each antenna site), as it clearly comes with higher deployment costs and may be used only for small cell and hot-spot scenarios [106].

A.2. Negligible latency components

In this section, we introduce further latency components in the model described in Section 5.2, and justify numerically why they bring negligible contributions compared to the other components for our MEC deployment problem.

Packet processing latency at UE – l^{ue} . According to [136,137], the packet processing latency at UE is assumed to be 2 Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) symbols for a SCS of 30 kHz, 3 OFDM symbols for 60 kHz SCS, and 4 OFDM symbols for 120 kHz SCS. The average OFDM symbol duration is $\frac{10^{-3}}{14.2\mu}$, where μ is 1, 2, and 3 for 30 kHz, 60 kHz, and 120 kHz SCS, respectively. Therefore, l^{ue} is in the range of tens of microseconds and thus negligible compared to other latency components in our context.

RU, DU, CU, Core node latency – l^{ru} , l^{du} , l^{cu} , l^{core} . The latency at each network node is assumed composed by two main components: *Processing* latency and *Queuing* latency.

The **processing latency** depends on the RAN functional split (refer to Fig. 13). For example, under Option 6, RUs are responsible for PHY functions while DUs execute the higher layers. Hence, for RU processing latency, we adopt the model in [138]; assuming CPU frequencies between 2 and 3.4 GHz and MCS from 5 to 27, we estimate the RU processing latency in a range between 0.05 ms and 0.5 ms. For DU, CU and Core processing latency we use the model in [139]. To compute DU and CU processing latency, we first calculate the overall latency, and then split it on DU or CU, depending on the disaggregated RAN option. By doing so, we find that we can ignore DU, CU, and Core processing latency altogether, as it is in the order of 10 μ s, especially considering new multi-core processing units on the market for both 5G RAN [140,141] and 5G Core [142].

We assume that the **queuing latency** is based on a $nD/D/1$ queuing model (i.e., a single server with a deterministic service time and n service request arrivals), which is also used in [143] to model user-aggregated periodic IoT traffic. Eq. (17) shows the expected Queuing time Q , where n_s is the number of users requesting service s , P is the average node processing time as discussed above, T_s is the average packet inter-arrival time for service s , and $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Erlang-B formula, used to calculate the probability that all servers in the queuing model are occupied, as in Eq. (18):

$$E[Q_{nD/D/1}] = \frac{(n_s - 1) \frac{P^2 n_s}{T_s}}{2n_s B\left(n_s - 2, \frac{T_s}{P}\right)}, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{B(n, a)} = 1 + \frac{a}{B(n-1, a)}, \quad \text{with } B(0, a) = 1. \quad (18)$$

We assume that vehicular services may be prioritized over other services due to their stringent latency requirements [88]. We compute the queuing latency based on processing latency and observe that it is negligible for all network nodes and services, compared to other latency components. For example, the average queuing latency for the 90% of RUs is lower than 40 μ s.

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